

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

Glossary

Set of one-pagers

WP5– Capacity building for stakeholder engagement

HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions under grant agreement No 101093921

Adaptation AGORA Glossary

Under the capacity building activities, Adaptation AGORA has been developing different materials. They range from multimedia materials, like videos, recordings of webinars/conferences, to sets of slides, as well as content for the development of the two Academies. Adaptation AGORA is not responsible for the use of the materials (CC BY).

1. Link to the material

See annexes

2. Potential key entries to search material.

Category: Glossary

Target: Consortium partners, researchers, practitioners.

3. Brief Introduction/Summary

Estimated time: 15 minutes reading approximately

Objective: Provide a common reference of terms, concepts, and sources relevant to climate change adaptation, supporting consistency across project outputs.

Type of resource: Excel file

Language: English

4. Key Challenges/ issues addressed

- Lack of shared understanding of technical terms.
- Risk of misinterpretation across disciplines and regions.
- Need for reliable references and consistent language in project deliverables.

5. What the Resource Offers

Practical Guidance: Clear definitions of climate change adaptation concepts, sources for each entry to ensure traceability and scientific rigor and a harmonised terminology base for all project partners and stakeholders.

Kohandamine AGORA sõnastik

Adaptation AGORA on võimekuse suurendamise eesmärgil välja töötanud erinevaid materjale, nt nagu multimeediasisu (videod, veebiseminaride/konverentside salvestused), slaidikomplektide, samuti kahe akadeemia arendamiseks mõeldud sisu. Adaptation Agora ei vastuta materjalide kasutamise eest (CC BY).

1. Link materjalile:

Vaata lisasid

2. Võimalikud märksõnad materjali otsimiseks.

Kategooria: Sõnastik

Sihtrühm: Konsortsiumi partnerid, teadlased, praktikud

3. Lühike sissejuhatus/kokkuvõte

Eeldatav aeg: umbes 15 minutit lugemiseks

Eesmärk: pakkuda ühine viide kliimamuutustega kohanemisega seotud terminitele, mõistetele ja allikatele, toetades projektide tulemuste ühtsust.

Ressursi tüüp: Excel-fail

Keel: inglise keel

4. Peamised väljakutsed/ lahendatavad probleemid

- Tehniliste terminite ühise mõistmise puudumine.
- Valesti tõlgendamise oht eri valdkondade ja piirkondade vahel.
- Vajadus usaldusväärsete viidete ja ühtse keele järele projekti tulemustes.

5. Mida ressurs pakub?

Praktilised juhised: kliimamuutustega kohanemise mõistete selged määratlused, iga sissekande allikad jälgitavuse ja teadusliku täpsuse tagamiseks ning ühtlustatud terminoloogiabaas kõikidele projektipartneritele ja sidusrühmadele.

Glossaire Adaptation AGORA

Dans le cadre des activités de renforcement des capacités, Adaptation AGORA a développé différents supports. Ceux-ci incluent des contenus multimédias, tels que des vidéos, enregistrements de webinaires/conférences, des ensembles de diapositives, ainsi que des contenus pour le développement de deux Académies. L'utilisation de ces contenus, mis à disposition sous licence Creative Commons (CC BY), relève de la responsabilité des utilisateurs et non du projet Adaptation Agora (CC BY)

1. Lien vers le contenu: Voir les annexes

2. Entrées clés potentielles pour rechercher du matériel.

Catégorie : Glossaire

Cible : Partenaires du consortium, chercheurs, praticiens.

3. Brève introduction/résumé

Durée estimée : environ 15 minutes de lecture

Objectif : fournir une référence commune des termes, concepts et sources pertinents pour l'adaptation au changement climatique, afin de garantir la cohérence entre les résultats des projets.

Type de ressource : fichier Excel

Langue : anglais

4. Principaux défis/problèmes abordés

- Manque de compréhension commune des termes techniques.
- Risque d'interprétation erronée entre les disciplines et les régions.
- Besoin de références fiables et d'un langage cohérent dans les livrables du projet.

5. Ce que la ressource offre

Conseils pratiques : Définitions claires des concepts liés à l'adaptation au changement climatique, sources pour chaque entrée afin de garantir la traçabilité et la rigueur scientifique, et base terminologique harmonisée pour tous les partenaires du projet et les parties prenantes.

AdaptationAGORA Glossar

Im Rahmen der Aktivitäten zur Kapazitätsentwicklung hat das Projekt Adaptation AGORA verschiedene Ressourcen entwickelt. Diese beinhalten multimediale Inhalte wie Videos, Aufzeichnungen von Webinaren/Konferenzen, Foliensätze sowie Inhalte für die Entwicklung der beiden Online-Akademien. Adaptation AGORA ist nicht verantwortlich für die Nutzung der Ressourcen (CC BY).

1. Link zur Ressource: Siehe Anhang

2. Potenzielle Suchbegriffe:

Kategorie: Glossar

Zielgruppe: Konsortialpartner, Forscher, Praktiker

3. Kurze Einführung/Zusammenfassung

Geschätzte Zeit: ca. 15 Minuten Lesezeit

Ziel: Bereitstellung einer gemeinsamen Referenz für Begriffe, Konzepte und Quellen im Zusammenhang mit der Anpassung an den Klimawandel, um die Konsistenz der Projektergebnisse zu gewährleisten.

Art der Ressource: Excel-Datei

Sprache: Englisch

4. Zentrale Herausforderungen/Probleme, die adressiert werden

- Fehlendes gemeinsames Verständnis technischer Begriffe.
- Risiko von Fehlinterpretationen zwischen verschiedenen Fachbereichen und Regionen.
- Notwendigkeit zuverlässiger Referenzen und einer einheitlichen Sprache in den Projektergebnissen.

5. Was die Ressource bietet

Praktische Leitlinien: Klare Definitionen der Konzepte zur Anpassung an den Klimawandel, Quellenangaben für jeden Eintrag zur Gewährleistung der Rückverfolgbarkeit und wissenschaftlichen Genauigkeit sowie eine harmonisierte Terminologiebasis für alle Projektpartner und Interessengruppen.

Adaptation AGORA Γλωσσάριο

Στο πλαίσιο των δραστηριοτήτων ανάπτυξης ικανοτήτων, το πρόγραμμα Adaptation AGORA έχει δημιουργήσει επιμορφωτικό και εκπαιδευτικό υλικό. Αυτό περιλαμβάνει πολυμεσικό υλικό, όπως βίντεο, μαγνητοσκοπημένα διαδικτυακά σεμινάρια/συνεδρία, παρουσιάσεις, καθώς και το περιεχόμενο που χρησιμοποιήθηκε για την ανάπτυξη των δύο διαδικτυακών Ακαδημιών. Το Adaptation Agora δεν φέρει ευθύνη για τη χρήση των υλικών (CC BY).

1. Σύνδεσμος προς το υλικό: Βλέπε παραρτήματα

2. Πιθανοί βασικοί όροι αναζήτησης του υλικού.

Κατηγορία: Γλωσσάριο

Ομάδες-Στόχοι: Εταίροι της κοινοπραξίας, ερευνητές, επαγγελματίες.

3. Σύντομη εισαγωγή/περίληψη

Εκτιμώμενος χρόνος: 15 λεπτά ανάγνωσης περίπου

Σκοπός: Η παροχή ενός κοινού σημείου αναφοράς για όρους, έννοιες και πηγές που σχετίζονται με την κλιματική προσαρμογή, με σκοπό τη διασφάλιση συνέπειας σε όλα τα παραδοτέα του έργου.

Τύπος υλικού: Αρχείο Excel

Γλώσσα: Αγγλικά

4. Βασικές προκλήσεις/ζητήματα που αντιμετωπίζονται

- Έλλειψη κοινής κατανόησης των τεχνικών όρων.
- Κίνδυνος παρερμηνείας μεταξύ διαφορετικών κλάδων και περιοχών.
- Ανάγκη για αξιόπιστες αναφορές και συνεπή χρήση γλώσσας στα παραδοτέα του έργου.

5. Τι προσφέρει το υλικό

Πρακτικές οδηγίες: Σαφείς ορισμοί των εννοιών που σχετίζονται με την προσαρμογής στην κλιματική αλλαγή, πηγές για κάθε λήμμα ώστε να διασφαλίζεται η ανιχνευσιμότητα και η επιστημονική εγκυρότητα, καθώς και μια εναρμονισμένη βάση ορολογίας για όλους τους εταίρους του έργου και τα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη.

Glossario di Adaptation AGORA

Nell'ambito delle attività di capacity building Adaptation AGORA ha sviluppato diversi materiali che spaziano da contenuti multimediali, come video e registrazioni di webinar/conferenze, presentazioni in power point, nonché contenuti per lo sviluppo delle due Accademie. Adaptation Agora non è responsabile dell'utilizzo dei materiali (CC BY)

1. Link Alla risorsa: vedi allegati

2. Parole chiave per la ricerca della risorsa:

Categoria: Glossario

Destinatari: Partner del consorzio, ricercatori, professionisti

3. Sintesi

Tempo stimato per la consultazione della risorsa: circa 15 minuti di lettura

Obiettivo: Fornire un riferimento comune di termini, concetti e fonti rilevanti per l'adattamento ai cambiamenti climatici, favorendo la coerenza tra i risultati del progetto.

Tipo di risorsa: file excel

Lingua: Inglese

4. Principali sfide/problematiche affrontate

- Mancanza di una comprensione condivisa dei termini tecnici
- Rischio di fraintendimenti tra discipline e regioni
- Necessità di riferimenti affidabili e di un linguaggio coerente nei risultati del progetto

5. Cosa offre la risorsa

- Guida pratica: definizioni chiare dei concetti legati all'adattamento ai cambiamenti climatici
- Fonti di riferimento: per ogni voce, che garantiscono tracciabilità e rigore scientifico
- Base terminologica armonizzata: a disposizione di tutti i partner del progetto e degli stakeholder

Glosario de Adaptation AGORA

En el marco de las actividades de desarrollo de capacidades, Adaptation AGORA ha elaborado diversos materiales. Estos abarcan desde materiales multimedia, como vídeos y grabaciones de seminarios web y conferencias, hasta conjuntos de diapositivas, así como contenidos para el desarrollo de las dos academias. Adaptation Agora no se hace responsable del uso de los materiales (CC BY).

1. Enlace al material: Ver anexos

2. Posibles entradas clave para buscar el material:

Categoría: Glosario

Destinatarios: Socios del consorcio, investigadores, profesionales.

3. Breve introducción/resumen

Tiempo estimado: 15 minutos de lectura aproximadamente

Objetivo: Proporcionar una referencia común de términos, conceptos y fuentes relevantes para la adaptación al cambio climático, favoreciendo la coherencia entre los resultados del proyecto.

Tipo de recurso: archivo Excel

Idioma: inglés

4. Retos clave/temas abordados

- Falta de comprensión común de los términos técnicos.
- Riesgo de malinterpretación entre disciplinas y regiones.
- Necesidad de referencias fiables y un lenguaje coherente en los resultados del proyecto.

5. Qué ofrece el recurso

Orientación práctica: definiciones claras de los conceptos relacionados con la adaptación al cambio climático, fuentes para cada entrada que garanticen la trazabilidad y el rigor científico, y una base terminológica armonizada para todos los socios del proyecto y las partes interesadas.

Adaptation AGORA ordlista

Adaptation AGORA har tagit fram olika material för kapacitetsutveckling. Dessa inkluderar allt från multimediamaterial, såsom videor och inspelningar av webbseminarier och konferenser, till bildsamlingar och material för utvecklingen av de två akademierna.

Adaptation AGORA ansvarar inte för hur materialen används (CC BY).

1. Länk till materialet: Se bilagor

2. Potentiella sökord.

Kategori: Ordlista

Målgrupp: Projektpartners, forskare, praktiker.

3. Kort introduktion/sammanfattning

Beräknad tid: Cirka 15 minuter

Syfte: Tillhandahålla en gemensam utgångspunkt för termer, begrepp och referenser som är relevanta för anpassning till klimatförändringar, vilket stöder konsekvent användning i projektets leveranser.

Typ av resurs: Excel-fil

Språk: engelska

4. Centrala umaningar/problem som behandlas

- Brist på gemensam förståelse av tekniska termer.
- Risk för feltolkningar mellan olika discipliner och regioner.
- Behov av tillförlitliga referenser och konsekvent språkbruk i projektleveranser.

5. Vad resursen erbjuder

Praktisk vägledning: Tydliga definitioner av begrepp som rör anpassning till klimatförändringar, referenser för varje post för att säkerställa spårbarhet och vetenskaplig stringens samt en harmoniserad terminologibas för alla projektpartners och intressenter.

Annex: Resource

Words and concepts	Definition	Definition Source
1		
2	IPCC's Fifth Sixth Assessment Report	https://www.ipcc.ch
3	Adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities. Various types of adaptation can be distinguished, including anticipatory and reactive adaptation, private and public adaptation, and autonomous and planned adaptation	Jordan, P.C., Ballard, H., Phillips, T.B. 2012. Key issues and new approaches for evaluating citizen-science learning outcomes. <i>Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment</i> 10: 307–308. DOI: 10.1890/1523-1739.2012.10.307
4	partnerships between scientists and non-scientists in which authentic data are collected, shared, and analyzed	
5	Tools based on climate change projects for local areas, e.g., including potential climate impacts, and suggested adaptation priorities. Such tools help stakeholders like decision makers, businesses, educators, scientists, communities and private persons to anticipate, plan for, and adapt to projected climatic changes	https://www.epa.gov/eatcd/what-is-climate-change-adaptation
6	Climate indices are diagnostic tools used to describe the state of the climate system and monitor climate. They are most often represented with a time series, where each point in time corresponds to one index value. An index can be constructed to describe almost any atmospheric event	https://clisat.etsi-cti.eui.it/guide/indexofclimaindices_table.html
7	Projections of future climate conditions via complex climate models	https://www.noaa.gov/products/paleoclimatology/climate-reconstruction
8	Reconstruction of a previous climate at a specific date or time, usually via observations or paleoclimatic studies	https://climate.copernicus.eu/climate-projections
9	The potential for adverse consequences for human or ecological systems, recognizing the diversity of values and objectives associated with such systems. In the context of climate change, risks can arise from potential impacts of climate change as well as human responses to climate change. Relevant adverse consequences include those on lives, livelihoods, health and well-being, economic, social and cultural assets and investments, infrastructure, services (including ecosystem services), ecosystems and species	https://apps.ipcc.ch/glossary/
10	"Reliable, credible, and accessible to users, acknowledges uncertainty, is communicated through a user-specific format, and is timely for user needs. It is developed by users and producers through valued interaction, while building trust, and increasing users' capacity for using the service and understanding the issue at hand. The service delivers benefits to the user and supports better decision-making for adaptation" (Bon et al., 2024, p.5)	(Bon et al., 2024, p.5)
11	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, Phase 5 or 6	https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmp
12	Collect citizen/stakeholders feedback on climate public services, governance or public outcomes, as well as on climate impacts	Loeffler, E., Bevard, J. (2021) <i>The Palgrave Handbook of Co-production of Public Services and Outcomes</i> . Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke, UK. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-53705-0_32
13	A positive effect that a policy or measure aimed at one objective has on another objective, thereby increasing the total benefit to society or the environment. Co-benefits are also referred to as ancillary benefits.	IPCC Glossary Search
14	Collaboratively creating outputs like tools or policy recommendations. A process that can add value and increase innovative potential through intentional experience design	https://www.nature.com/sfn/knowledge-co-creation https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-53705-0_2
15	To articulate the implicit and explicit meaning of a particular term together with one or more people, in this case climate change adaptation strategies, policies or actions.	
16	To create ways in which challenges can be addressed together with one or more people, implementing different methodologies and/or approaches such as lateral thinking to propose innovative solutions to current pressing climate change related issues. It may also include devising effective, analytical-deliberative procedures/processes and sustainable problem-solving techniques and strategies directly applicable to the challenges that need to be addressed.	CO-DESIGN (English meaning - Cambridge Dictionary)
17	To determine the best manner to satisfy the requirements for an expected output together with one or more people or organizations. This includes analytical deliberative procedures for engagement of citizen/stakeholders related to the creation of adaptation projects and evaluating baseline requirements and consider all potential alternatives to solve a particular climate risk or impact challenge.	CO-DEVELOP (English meaning - Cambridge Dictionary)
18	Explore the perspectives of key actors within co-production processes to assess the challenges and opportunities faced, and describe this idea to capture the process through which boundaries might be actively subverted through sustained engagement between the origins of multiple, diverse perspectives.	Howarth, C., Lane, M., Morse-Jones, S., Brooks, K., & Viner, D. (2022). The "co-in co-production of climate action: challenging boundaries within and between science, policy and practice. <i>Global Environmental Change</i> , 72, 102445.
19	To validate potential solutions or partial solutions to a particular challenge or issue (only) with one or more people. This implies considering available information, processes and how adequate the solution is in meeting the needs and expectations of stakeholders.	Couldn't find any definitions online
20	Enlist citizens in ensuring that pathways to public climate adaptation outcomes are successfully implemented	Loeffler, E., Bevard, J. (2021) <i>The Palgrave Handbook of Co-production of Public Services and Outcomes</i> . Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke, UK. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-53705-0_32
21	Co-regulation and co-management give the right to participants to be directly included in designing, revising or reviewing regulations and risk management measures, rule-making processes or programmes for monitoring risks.	IPCC (2020) Involving stakeholders in the risk governance process. <i>Luxembourg: EFPL International Risk Governance Center</i> . DOI: 10.5979/efpl-irgc-2020-43
22	Iterative and collaborative processes involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways towards a sustainable future" (Nerström, et al., 2020:83).	(Nerström, et al., 2020:83)
23	Input delivered by communities, e.g., local inhabitants have worked on the data or participatory methods have been included	https://mrcs.org/en/exploring-topical-environmental-sustainability/climate-equity-and-engagement
24	Coordinated Regional Downscaling Experiment A Global Climate Model (GCM) can provide reliable prediction information on scales of around 1000 by 1000 km covering what could be a vastly differing landscape (from very mountainous to flat coastal plains for example) with greatly varying potential for floods, droughts or other extreme events. Regional Climate Models (RCM) and Empirical Statistical Downscaling (ESD), applied over a limited area and driven by GCMs can provide information on much smaller scales supporting more detailed impact and adaptation assessment and planning, which is vital in many vulnerable regions of the world.	https://fordis.org/about/what-is-regional-downscaling
25	Breaking down costs, comparing against other scenarios, and/or projecting future costs.	https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/cost-benefit-analysis
26	European branch of the international CORDEX initiative. In 2009 the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) established the Task Force for Regional Climate Downscaling (TFRCO), which created the CORDEX initiative to generate regional climate change projections for all terrestrial regions of the globe within the timeline of the Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) and beyond.	https://www.euro-cordex.net/66037/Mydex.pdf

Words and concepts	Definition	Definition Source
1		
27	Global Climate Model: Complex mathematical representation of the major climate system components (atmosphere, land surface, ocean, and sea ice), and their interactions. Earth's energy balance between the four components is the key to long-term climate prediction.	https://www.gfdl.noaa.gov/climate-modeling/
28	Impact: Assessing the effects of climate change towards a pre-defined spatial scale	https://www.noaa.gov/education/resource-collections/climate/climate-change-impacts/
29	Interactivity: Chosen to decide of tools can be used outside of their own scale (e.g. Regional tool can be used locally). The reference refers to scaling-up, but interactivity refers to the ability to scale up and down the tools output to suit the user's needs.	https://www.gfdl.noaa.gov/education/resource-collections/climate/climate-change-impacts/health-implications-interactive-tool/#p=1:scaling
30	IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change: the United Nations body for assessing the science related to climate change.	https://www.ipcc.ch/
31	Policy Frameworks: Used to adopt policies in a coherent and effective way. They provide an overarching strategy (including a methodology) of how to tackle an issue or policy-dependent situation.	https://www.bfgh.se.uk/operate-information-policy-framework/
32	RD4: Regional Climate Model: Numerical climate prediction model forced by specified lateral and ocean conditions from a general circulation model (GCM) or observation-based dataset (reanalysis) that simulates atmospheric and land surface processes, while accounting for high-resolution topographical data, land-sea contrasts, surface characteristics, and other components of the Earth system.	https://glossary.armetec.org/wiki/Regional_climate_model
33	RCP: Representative Concentration Pathway: Greenhouse gas concentration trajectory adopted by the IPCC. Four RCPs produced from Integrated Assessment Models were selected from the published literature and are used in the Fifth IPCC Assessment Report as a basis for the climate predictions and projections presented in WG1 AR5 Chapters 11 to 14.	https://www.ipcc.ch/ipcc/docs/working_group1/wg1_ar5_chapter11_04.pdf
34	RCP 2.6: One pathway where radiative forcing peaks at approximately 3 W/m ² before 2100 and then declines (the corresponding ECP assuming constant emissions after 2100)	https://www.ipcc-data.org/data/inventory/glossary/glossary_1.html
35	RCP 4.5 & RCP 6.0: Two intermediate stabilisation pathways in which radiative forcing is stabilised at approximately 4.5 W/m ² and 6.0 W/m ² after 2100 (the corresponding ECPs assuming constant concentrations after 2100)	https://www.ipcc-data.org/data/inventory/glossary/glossary_1.html
36	RCP 8.5: One high pathway for which radiative forcing reaches greater than 8.5 W/m ² by 2100 and continues to rise for some amount of time (the corresponding ECP assuming constant emissions after 2100 and constant concentrations after 2300)	https://www.ipcc-data.org/data/inventory/glossary/glossary_1.html
37	Resilience: Communities ability to withstand hazards from climate change; higher resilience means communities can withstand greater hazards without quality of life dropping. Related tools may provide measures to improve this ability.	https://www.ipcc-data.org/data/inventory/glossary/glossary_1.html
38	Risk: Assessing likelihood to be subject to a certain hazard and protecting future damages given no policy or no mitigation efforts (to showcase a worst-best case scenario)	https://www.ipcc-data.org/data/inventory/glossary/glossary_1.html
39	SRES: Special Report on Emission Scenarios: Comparable to baseline Emission Scenarios; following how emissions are regulated by different policy Scenarios; used in previous IPCC Assessment Reports (AR4 and earlier)	https://www.ipcc.ch/nareset/nareset/201803/nareset-en.pdf
40	SSPs: Shared Socioeconomic Pathways: Examine how global society, demographics and economics might change over the next century and are now being used as important inputs for the latest climate models, feeding into the Sixth IPCC Assessment Report	https://www.ccbiorbit.org/epi/planer-how-shared-socioeconomic-pathways-explore-future-climate-change
41	Tipping Points: Concept showing scenarios where climate cannot recover to original levels. A common example is Sea level rise. past a certain point, certain regions will not be able to recover their sea-level extent or concentration; this principle can be applied to a plethora of climate variables like temperature, biodiversity loss, precipitation, sea level rise.	https://www.studymeter.co.uk/collect/plan/environmental-science/climate-change/planer-how-shared-socioeconomic-pathways-explore-future-climate-change
42	WMO: World Meteorological Organization	https://www.wmo.int/
43	Vulnerable communities: Vulnerability here can be defined as "the characteristics and circumstances of a community, system or asset that make it susceptible to the damaging effects of a (climate) hazard"	https://www.unisdr.org/we/inform/portal/en/content/view/full/4331_1_sandalframeworkfordrem.pdf
44	Multicultural groups: Including or involving people of several different ethnicities (= groups of people with a shared culture, tradition, language, history, etc.)	https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/multicultural
45	Media literacy: Media literacy includes all the technical, cognitive, social, civic and creative capabilities that allow a citizen to access, have a critical understanding of the media and interact with it. It refers to all kind of media (television, radio, press), through all kind of channels (traditional, internet, social media) and to all ages. A key stone in all possible definitions of media literacy is the development of critical thinking by the user.	https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/erpnet/groups-register/erpnet-groups/consult/engage-er8-do-group/Detail_groupDetail/groupID/2541
46	Climate change disinformation: Climate disinformation is the intentional dissemination of false information related to climate change and climate action. It can take many forms, from hard denial and conspiracy theories to softer, more insidious disinformation that seeks to muddy the waters by claiming that climate change is not man-made or as bad as scientists are saying and therefore requires no urgent action.	https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/climate-disinformation_en
47	Fact-checking: Use of an evidence-based method to verify the accuracy of claims made in the public sphere	https://fact.com/code-of-standards/
48	Disinformation: Disinformation is understood as verifiably false or misleading information that is created, presented and disseminated for economic gain or to intentionally deceive the public, and may cause public harm. Public harm comprises threats to democratic political and policy-making processes as well as public goods such as the protection of EU citizens' health, the environment or security.	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52018000038
49	EUOPA: European Climate Risk Assessment	https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/european-climate-risk-assessment
50	NASA: National Aeronautics and Space Administration	https://www.nasa.gov/
51	NOAA: National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	https://www.noaa.gov/

